

THE FACTORS AFFECT CONSUMERS' INTENTION TO PURCHASE ECO-FRIENDLY BAGS IN HAIPHONG CITY

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on understanding the factors that influence consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City. There are 5 factors proposed to be included in the research model. However, with the collected data from 328 Hai Phong consumers tested using the SMARTPLS software, the testing results showed that 3 factors positively influence the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags, which the factor with the greatest influence is "Expectations for a good life for future generations" (KVCS) (0.394), followed by the factor "Personal Image" (HACN) (0.219) and finally the factor "Attitude towards eco-friendly bags" (TD) (0.150). The results of testing the factors "Green Marketing Programs" (MX) and "Environmental Understanding" (HBMT) are not statistically significant enough to influence the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City. With the above testing results, the research team exchanged and discussed ideas to convey messages and encourage consumers to use environmentally friendly bags.

KEYWORDS

Influencing factors, purchase intention, eco-friendly bags, consumers, Hai Phong City.

1. Introduction:

According to a United Nations report, the world uses an average of 5 trillion plastic bags every year. It takes hundreds of years to decompose those nylon bags, while recycling is very expensive and difficult. Therefore, to limit the use of nylon bags, many countries in the world have implemented a wide range of campaigns to reduce plastic bags, instead using environmentally friendly bag products, often starting from the system of supermarkets and shops.

In Vietnam, plastic bags have been used by people for many recent decades and their harmful effects on the environment are very serious and alarming. Therefore, the issue of reducing the use of plastic bags and increasing the use of environmentally friendly bags is a major concern of Vietnam in general and Hai Phong City in particular. Hai Phong Department of Industry and Trade launched the campaign to *Limit the use of non-degradable plastic bags and implement "anti-plastic waste"* in the city from 12 to 18/12/2022. Thousands of leaflets and posters were distributed to 25 locations in the city including supermarkets, shopping centers, convenience store chains, and traditional markets (Hai Phong Department of Industry and Trade, 2022). Manufacturing business towards a sustainable green environment has become a top goal of businesses, especially supermarkets.

Changing people's habit of not using plastic bags is difficult but not impossible. Therefore, researching factors influencing consumers' intention to buy eco-friendly bags in Hai Phong city to propose solutions to preserve the environment is a very essential issue.

2. Theoretical background:

2.1. Some relevant definitions:

- *Green purchase intention*

Green purchase intention can be defined as a consumer's relative strength in the intention to perform a certain behavior (Aman et al., 2012) or as a specific form of environmentally friendly behavior expressed through consumers' interest in the environment (Zia-ur-Rehman and Dost, 2013).

The widely accepted theory of rational action to explain the green buying behavior of consumers is presented by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975). It affirms that consumers' attitudes toward environmental issues will strongly determine their actual behavior and purchase of green products (Albayrak et al., 2013).

Theories of consumer behavior have strengthened the theoretical basis and demonstrated that the consumer's intention to buy green products has a strong impact on the purchase decision (Kalafatis et al., 1999). At the same time, the theory of planned action (Ajzen, 1991) asserts that purchase intention is an important factor in determining the actual buying behavior of consumers. This means that when the intention to buy a green product increases, the probability that a consumer purchases a green product also increases.

- *Eco-friendly products:*

According to Decree No. 19/2015/ND-CP of the Government, *an environmentally friendly product is a product that meets the criteria of eco-labels and is certified with an eco-label*. For a product to be assessed as an eco-friendly product, it must meet the eco-label criteria (which is a necessary condition) and must be certified with the eco-label (which is a sufficient condition).

- *Green consumption*

According to researchers around the world on green consumption behavior, green consumers can be understood according to different characteristics and levels. *A green consumer is anyone whose purchasing behavior is influenced by environmental concerns* (Shrum et al., 1995), particularly those who "avoid products harmful to their health or the health of others, avoid products that are detrimental to the environment during the production process, as well as products wasting energy and materials that threaten the sustainability of the environment" (Strong, 1996).

In another study cited in Suplico (2009), the Roper Foundation identified five consumer market segments in the US based on their level of commitment to the environment. *Firstly*, "true-blue green", consumers strongly believe that their actions have an impact on the environment. They are willing to invest more in green products and participate in ecological activities such as recycling and organic waste treatment. They are the most environmentally conscious group of consumers and will buy green products from companies that are truly environmentally conscious. *Secondly*, the "greenback green", consumers also invest more in green products but are not ready to participate in environmental protection activities. To protect their lives, these consumers tend to engage in environmental activities only through monetary means. *Thirdly*, "sprouts" are consumers who support environmental regulations but are less able to pay for green products. *Fourthly*, "grousers" believe that it is not their responsibility to solve environmental problems. *Ultimately*, "basic brown" is the person who does not put any personal, commercial, or political effort into tackling ecological problems. Therefore, this definition shows that consumers in the first 3 segments are all concerned about the environment, but only the first 2 segments are willing to pay for environmentally friendly products. The remaining two segments are mostly not responsible for environmental issues.

According to Kumar and Ghodeswar (2015), green consumers are described as those who are concerned about the environmental consequences of consuming their products and intend to change their purchasing and consumption behavior to reduce their impact on the environment.

Recently, Vietnam has stimulated green consumption demand, and at the same time, the Vietnam Green Purchasing Network (VNPN) was established by the Vietnam Productivity Center (VPC) in 2009 and is a bridge between Vietnam and International Green Purchasing Network (IGPN) as well as green purchasing networks of countries in the region and around the world. However, compared to other countries in the region, the requirement for green products in the Vietnamese market as well as consumer awareness is still limited. Products are labeled with unclear environmental labels and have not been favored by consumers. Vietnamese businesses are still cautious in investing, using technology, and management methods, and applying appropriate management systems to produce products that meet labeling requirements. On the other hand, the criteria for green products are currently still quite restricted in quantity and only for a certain type of product. Therefore, Vietnam will need to have promotional activities to support businesses to quickly integrate and raise consumer awareness when choosing to buy products. At the same time, the national policies and regulations are becoming clearer and more specific to facilitate green products to gain a foothold and develop in the Vietnamese market.

2.2. Some theories about consumer behavior:

Consumer behavior theory: Maximize consumption benefits within the limits of income, product price, and consumer preferences. Consumers' shopping behavior is reflected in finding, purchasing, using, and evaluating products and services that they expect to meet their personal needs (Bennett, 1988). Consumer behavior is understood as a series of purchasing decisions that each

individual or group of consumers must make over time regarding the choice of using a product, service, idea, or activity. (Munnukka, 2008)

Theory of Reasoned Action - TRA. Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) proposed the Rational Behavior model (TRA) to explain and predict behavioral intentions in the case of product adoption. This theory holds that “intention” is the best predictor of final behavior and that intention is simultaneously determined by attitudes and subjective norms.

(1) *Attitude:* An emotional state expressing an individual's behavior through gestures, speech, facial expressions, images, and things related to the product.

(2) *Subjective standards.* Behavioral intentions are influenced by stakeholders' attitudes toward the use of the product, and people's motivation to use products is influenced by stakeholders' behaviors and desires.

Theory of Planned Behavior – TPB. Ajzen's (1991) TPB theory posits that people perform a certain behavior if they believe that the behavior will have valuable outcomes. TPB theory includes a set of relationships between attitudes, subjective norms, perceived control, and behavioral intentions.

(3) *Perceived behavioral control:* Is an individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to perform that behavior (related to available resources, knowledge, and opportunities needed to apply)

2.3. Research model and hypothesis:

Figure 1. Proposed research model

Research hypothesis:

H1: Attitude towards eco-friendly bags is positively correlated with the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags.

H2: Environmental knowledge is positively correlated with the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags.

H3: Personal image has a positive correlation with the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags.

H4: The Green Marketing program is positively correlated with the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags.

H5: Expectations for a good life for future generations have a positive impact on the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags.

Table 1. Research variables and measures

Ordinal number	Encryption	Research measures	Reference source
1	TD	Attitude toward eco-friendly bags	Cai Trinh Minh Quoc et al (2020) Pham Thu Huong and Tran Minh Thu (2019)
1.1	TD1	Using eco-friendly bags is the right idea	
1.2	TD2	Using eco-friendly bags is a bright idea.	
1.3	TD3	I like the idea of using eco-friendly bags.	
1.4	TD4	I feel comfortable using eco-friendly bags.	
2	HBMT	Environmental knowledge	Anees Ahmad, K.S. Thyagaraj (2015)
2.1	HBMT1	I have learned a lot about recycling	
2.2	HBMT2	I understand the environmental terms and symbols on the product packaging	
2.3	HBMT3	I am extremely knowledgeable about environmental issues.	
3	HACN	Personal image	Pham Thi Lan Huong (2014)
3.1	HACN1	Participating in environmental protection activities helps me be highly appreciated by society	
3.2	HACN2	Taking part in environmental conservation activities makes me special in the eyes of others	
3.3	HACN3	I would be considered backward if I did not participate in environmental protection activities.	
4	MX	Green Marketing programs	Cai Trinh Minh Quoc et al (2020)
4.1	MX1	Supermarkets carry out many green marketing and environmental protection campaigns.	
4.2	MX2	Supermarkets implement many policies to promote environmentally friendly bags	
4.3	MX3	Supermarkets implement many policies to encourage customers to use eco-friendly bags.	
5	KVCS	Expectations for a good life for future generations	Vo Thi Bach Hoa (2014)
5.1	KVCS1	I hope future generations will live in a cleaner environment.	

5.2	KVCS2	I hope that future generations will not have to suffer the severe consequences of natural disasters due to climate change.	Pham Thu Huong and Tran Minh Thu (2019)
5.3	KVCS3	I hope that future generations will be healthy, reducing the number of people getting sick due to the harmful effects of plastic bag waste.	
6	YDM	The intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags	
6.1	YDM1	I want to buy environmentally friendly products	
6.2	YDM2	I will make an effort to buy environmentally friendly products	
6.3	YDM3	I would like to consume environmentally friendly products	
6.4	YDM4	I have a desire to encourage people to purchase environmentally friendly products.	

Source: Compilation of the research team

3. Research Methods

3.1. Data collection methods

Based on theory and an overview of research on factors affecting consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City, the factors put into the research model include 5 independent variables: (i) *Attitude towards eco-friendly bags (TD)*; (ii) *Environmental Understanding (HBMT)*; (iii) *Personal Image (HACN)*; (iv) *Green Marketing programs (MX)*; (v) *Expectations for a good life for future generations (KVCS)* affect the dependent variable "*The intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city*" (YDM).

The survey was built with a 5-point Likert scale:

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Agree
5. Strongly agree

After developing the survey questionnaire, the research team conducted in-depth interviews with 5 consumers in Hai Phong city who were knowledgeable and had used environmentally friendly bags. The survey was completed based on the feedback from the interviewees. Next, the research team conducted a randomized pilot survey for an additional 10 consumers. Preliminary survey results show that all opinions agree with the factors included in the model. Based on the preliminary survey, the research team completed the survey form and conducted a large-scale survey through the link (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfDhNjLRP38PZFhGpqK6OJhWF_8BNNynY1s2V1bRiEUXUcnZQ/viewform?usp=sf_link) to consumers living in Hai Phong city.

The data collection method implemented by the research team is based on the convenience sampling method and the "snowball" method - the method of finding the next subject is based on the suggestion or introduction of the interviewed subject - to ensure sufficient sample size as required. The number of votes surveyed and included in the analysis was 328 votes.

3.2. Data processing method

A quantitative research method was carried out to process research data collected from the survey of consumers in Hai Phong City on their intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags. SMARTPLS software is used to test hypotheses and evaluate the impact of factors.

Step 1: Evaluate the measurement model.

Evaluation of the measurement model is based on considering the values of the quality of the observed variables (Outer loadings), the reliability of the scale (Cronbach's Alpha), the convergence (Convergence), and Discriminant Validity.

Step 2: Evaluate the structural model.

After evaluating the satisfactory measurement model, evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, the path coefficient, the overall coefficient determining R squared, and the impact coefficient f squared.

4. Research results:

4.1. Description of survey participants

Figure 2. Occupation of survey participants

Source: Survey results

328 people participated in the survey, of which: 93 high school students (28%); 35 college/university students (11%); 144 officers/ civil servants/ workers (44%); 52 self-employed workers (16%), and other job positions are 4 people (1%).

Figure 3. Gender of survey participants

Source: Survey results

The total number of survey participants was 328 people, including 212 women (65%), 99 men (30%), and the remaining 17 people who did not want to specify their gender (5%).

4.2. Test results

4.2.1. Results of assessing the quality of observed variables in the measurement model

4.2.1.1. Check the quality of observed variables.

The quality of observed variables is evaluated through outer loading. The quality of observed variables affecting consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Outer loadings of factors affecting consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City.

	HACN	HBMT	KVCS	MX	TD	YDM
HACN1	0.913					
HACN2	0.939					
HACN3	0.881					
HBMT1		0.930				
HBMT2		0.938				
HBMT3		0.942				
KVCS1			0.974			
KVCS2			0.958			
KVCS3			0.971			
MX1				0.946		

MX2				0.951		
MX3				0.945		
TD1					0.945	
TD2					0.961	
TD3					0.948	
TD4					0.950	
YDM1						0.958
YDM2						0.943
YDM3						0.956
YDM4						0.937

Source: Testing results of the research team

The results from Table 2 show that outer loadings of all correlation coefficients, the sum of the variables affecting the intention to buy eco-friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City are > 0.7. (Hair & et al, 2016) shows that the observed variables are significant.

4.2.1.2. Check the reliability of the scale.

Assessing the reliability of the scale of factors affecting consumers' intention to purchase eco-friendly bags in Hai Phong city on PLS-SEM through two main indexes: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR).

Table 3. Reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) and overall reliability of factors affecting consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City.

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
HACN	0.898	0.902	0.936	0.831
HBMT	0.930	0.932	0.955	0.877
KVCS	0.966	0.967	0.978	0.936
MX	0.943	0.943	0.963	0.897
TD	0.965	0.967	0.974	0.904
YDM	0.963	0.963	0.973	0.900

Source: Testing results of the research team

According to Table 3, after analyzing the reliability test by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the factor, the results are: *Personal image (HACN)* reached 0.898; *Environmental understanding (HBMT)* reached 0.930; *Expectations for a good life for future generations (KVCS)* reached 0.966;

Green Marketing programs (MX) reached 0.943; *Attitude towards environmentally friendly bags (TD)* reached 0.965; *The intention to buy environmentally friendly bags (YDM)* reached 0.963. Therefore, all the scales satisfy the condition > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and do not violate any rule to exclude variables, so all variables are acceptable in terms of reliability.

The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables is also > 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). As a result, the scale has reliable analytical significance and is used in subsequent factor analysis.

4.2.1.3. Convergence

According to the data analysis results in Table 3, the average variance index is extracted AVE (Average Variance Extracted) of the factors: *Personal image (HACN)* reached 0.831; *Environmental understanding (HBMT)* reached 0.877; *Expectations for a good life for future generations (KVCS)* reached 0.936; *Green Marketing programs (MX)* reached 0.897; *Attitude towards eco-friendly bags (TD)* reached 0.904; *The intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags (YDM)* reached 0.900.

Therefore, the average variance extracted AVE (Average Variance Extracted) of all variables is > 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), which shows that the model satisfies the conditions of convergence.

4.2.1.4. Discriminant Validity

The results in Table 4 of the Fornell-Larcker index of the model researching factors affecting the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City show that the factors are: Personal image (HACN); Environmental understanding (HBMT); Expectations of a good life for future generations (KVCS); Green Marketing programs (MX); Attitude towards eco-friendly bags (TD); The intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags (YDM) ensures discrimination because all on-diagonal AVE square root values are higher than their off-diagonal values. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, the two criteria including the cross-loading coefficient and Fornell and Larcker's criteria have met the conditions.

Table 4. Fornell-Larcker criteria of the model to research factors affecting the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city

	HACN	HBMT	KVCS	MX	TD	YDM
HACN	0.911					
HBMT	0.738	0.937				
KVCS	0.516	0.484	0.968			
MX	0.611	0.658	0.653	0.947		
TD	0.509	0.552	0.628	0.574	0.951	
YDM	0.647	0.616	0.727	0.660	0.633	0.949

Source: Testing results of the research team

The test results in Table 5 give the results of the HTMT index on the discriminant between the factors affecting the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City. If according to Garson (2016), the discriminant of the variables is guaranteed (because all are < 1). According to Henseler et al (2015), if this value is below 0.9, the discriminant value will be

guaranteed. The HTMT value in Table 5 shows the discriminant properties of all factors included in the model.

Table 5. HTMT index of the model researching factors affecting the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city

	HACN	HBMT	KVCS	MX	TD	YDM
HACN						
HBMT	0.808					
KVCS	0.552	0.509				
MX	0.663	0.703	0.684			
TD	0.541	0.579	0.651	0.601		
YDM	0.694	0.650	0.753	0.693	0.654	

Source: Testing results of the research team

4.2.1.5. Function value f^2

The function value f^2 represents the level of impact of the structure (factor) when removed from the model. The f^2 values are 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 corresponding to small, medium, and large impact values (Cohen, 1988) of the exogenous variable. If the effect size was < 0.02 , it was considered to have no effect.

Table 6. Summary table of f^2 values

	HACN	HBMT	KVCS	MX	TD	YDM
HACN						0.059
HBMT						0.013
KVCS						0.216
MX						0.015
TD						0.035
YDM						

Source: Testing results of the research team

In this model, in Table 6 we see that KVCS (0.216), HACN (0.059), and TD (0.035) have effects on the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City with $f^2 > 0.15$ considered to have an average impact. The factors HBMT (0.013) and MX (0.015) with $f^2 < 0.02$ are considered to not influence YDM.

4.2.2. Results of assessing the level of impact using structural models

4.2.2.1. Evaluate impact relationships.

The relationship and influence level of factors affecting the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City on SMARTPLS is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Factors affecting the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City

Source: SMARTPLS test results of the research team

The results of Bootstrap analysis to evaluate the impact relationships are shown in Table 7. Accordingly, the factors "Personal Image" (HACN), "Expectations for a good life for future generations hybrid" (KVCS), and "Attitude towards environmentally friendly bags" (TD) have P Values <0.05, which reflects that these factors are statistically significant enough to show a positive relationship with consumers' intention to purchase eco-friendly bags in Hai Phong city. Hypotheses H1; H3; H4 are accepted.

The factors "Environmental understanding" (HBMT), and "Green Marketing programs" (MX) have P Values > 0.05, showing that these factors are not statistically significant enough to express a positive relationship on the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city. Hypotheses H2; and H5 are rejected.

Table 7. Path Coefficient of the structural model

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
HACN => YDM	0.219	0.228	0.064	3.417	0.001
HBMT => YDM	0.108	0.098	0.073	1.468	0.143
KVCS => YDM	0.394	0.390	0.074	5.314	0.000
MX => YDM	0.112	0.116	0.069	1.625	0.105
TD => YDM	0.150	0.149	0.070	2.150	0.032

Source: Testing results of the research team

The test results in Table 7 show that with 95% confidence, "Expectations for a good life for future generations" (KVCS) have the strongest impact on people's intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong city with an impact of 0.394; next is the factor "Personal Image" (HACN) with an impact level of 0.219, the factor "Attitude towards environmentally friendly bags" (TD) with an impact level of 0.150.

4.2.2.2. Evaluate the overall coefficient of determination R^2 (R square)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis give the R^2 value, reflecting the level of explanation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. The R^2 index measures the overall coefficient of determination (R-square value), which is an index to measure the degree of model fit of the data (the model's explanatory ability). According to Hair et al (2010), R-square values are suggested at 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25.

Table 8. Explanation coefficient of the independent variable for the dependent variable (R Square)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
YDM	0.663	0.658

Source: Testing results of the research team

The results from Table 8 show that R^2 equal to 0.663 and adjusted R^2 equal to 0.658 are appropriate in this research case, thus the independent variables in the model explained 66.3% of "The intention to purchase eco-friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city".

4.2.2.3. Reliability Index Rating (SRMR)

Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR): This index indicates the suitability of the research model. According to Hu & Bentler (1999), normally a suitable model will have an SRMR value of less than 0.08.

Table 9. The reliability index Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.038	0.038

Source: Testing results of the research team

According to the research results SRMR in Table 9 of the research model is 0.038, less than 0.08. Therefore, this model is suitable for data analysis.

5. Discussion and conclusion:

Among the 5 factors considered, four factors at the 5% significance level show an impact on the "Intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City". Among them, "Expectations for a good life for future generations" (KVCS) has the strongest impact on the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City with an impact level of 0.394, showing the desire to create a green life and a sustainable future is the most decisive factor in the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city,

meaning when the expectation of a good life for future generations increases by 1 unit, it will increase consumers' intention to buy environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong city by 0.394 units. The next factor is "Personal Image" (HACN) with an impact level of 0.219, showing that when personal image increases by 1 unit, it will encourage the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city by 0.219 units. The factor "Attitude towards eco-friendly bags" (TD) with an influence level of 0.150 shows that when this factor increases by 1 unit, it will successfully promote consumers' intention to buy environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong city by 0.150 units.

From the survey results and testing the influence of factors in the model on the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong City, the research team proposes the following suggestions:

- The factor "*Expectations for a good life for future generations*" has the strongest influence. Therefore, to develop a positive attitude towards eco-friendly bags as well as increase the intention to use environmentally friendly bags, communication activities of the government and businesses should focus on propagating consumer expectations, emphasizing the good things that using environmentally friendly bags can bring for the environment, for the lives of future generations of themselves and others around them. Media programs should also strongly convey the negative consequences of environmental destruction for the survival of consumers and their loved ones instead of only promoting the positive benefits of consuming eco-friendly bags, thus using eco-friendly bags as a good way to reduce their worries.

- It can be seen that the more modern life is, the more consumers care about the quality of life, aim for a future of sustainable development, and also want to affirm their "*Personal image*" in this new era. In recent years, in the context of environmental pollution problems becoming more and more serious, a green lifestyle has gradually become the trend of the times, especially among young consumer groups. They are very interested in protecting the environment, thereby also shaping their lifestyle and affirming their personality as a new-age citizen and a responsible consumer. As a result, when designing communication messages, managers and policymakers can build the image of individuals with a green lifestyle accompanying environmentally friendly bag products. Besides, managers can identify individuals who have a green lifestyle and care about their image, then highlight their beauty when using eco-bags or have ideas to commend them and invite them to participate in campaigns and propaganda activities about using environmentally friendly bags.

- The factor "*Attitude towards environmentally friendly bag products*" is also one of the important factors that determine the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags. Therefore, to increase positive attitudes towards environmentally friendly bag products, communication to increase awareness of environmental factors and awareness of environmentally friendly bag products is essential. Media messages should emphasize community responsibility, the causes of environmental problems, and highlight the advantages and environmental benefits of eco-friendly bag products as well and focus on developing durable, beautiful eco-friendly bag products that are suitable for consumers' needs. Increasing awareness and thereby changing consumer attitudes towards environmentally friendly bag products will help increase the intention to purchase and use environmentally friendly bags in the future.

Conclusion

Initial research results show the relationship between factors affecting consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City, with a small sample size of 328 survey votes collected and analyzed, along with convenient and random surveys, so this is also a limitation in sample size and survey quality. Furthermore, with 5 factors included in the new model, it only explains 66.3% of “*The intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags of consumers in Hai Phong city*”. In addition, there are only 3 statistically meaningful factors, the two factors are not statistically significant enough to conclude, showing there are other factors that also affect consumers' intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags in Hai Phong City. With the research results considered as a direction for further research on the intention to purchase environmentally friendly bags, in the future, the research team can expand the survey, research additional factors, and select respondents in a targeted way to increase sample size and quality of the surveys as well as the model's level of explanation.

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